

DEVELOPING WRITING SKILLS INCLUDING SPECIFIC VOCABULARY

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ABSTRACT

Completely writing inside learning a language against incorrect conception is one direction acquiring knowledge for difficult subject in our modern area. Since both dashes and quotations exist in both languages, it's common for non-fluent speakers of either language to switch these up. In order to improve your English writing skills, you must familiarize yourself with the formal rules that are specific to the language. You might find some value in getting a textbook on grammar and learning all the rules that way, but you don't really need to. By simply carefully studying reading material in English, you will be able to see how things need to be written in practice. Most importantly, don't take anything for granted.

KEYWORDS: Summary, fluent body, paragraphs, signal relationships, IELTS exam, verbal stimulation, word consciousness, comprehension, National Reading Panel, lexical resources, sell merchandise, audience, sound firm, writing format, coherence, proficiency, early and final composing.

INTRODUCTION

Do you want to know how to improve your English writing skills? Do you want to know how to write correct sentences without it being a painful task? Here are some tips to help you feel more confident with writing, and improve your English writing skills: 1. Read as much as you can. ... An useful way to improve your English writing skills is to start your paragraphs with a topic sentence: i.e. a

sentence that explains what you are going to write about. Continue with supporting sentences: i.e. sentences that provide more information about the topic. Finish with a conclusion: i.e. it is generally a summary of the ideas developed in the body of the paragraph. Learn how to make transitions between paragraphs to signal relationships between ideas so as to create a fluent body of text. So clearly, the first step to improve writing skills is improving your grammar and vocabulary.

In fact, one of the biggest mistakes students who want to take part in the IELTS exam make is to start by learning the techniques of the IELTS exam however the first step should be improving your general English knowledge. Do you want to know how to improve your English writing skills? Do you want to know how to write correct sentences without it being a painful task? Here are some tips to help you feel more confident with writing, and improve your English writing skills: 1. Read as much as you can. ... An useful way to improve your English writing skills is to start your paragraphs with a topic sentence: i.e. a sentence that explains what you are going to write about. Continue with supporting sentences: i.e. sentences that provide more information about the topic. Finish with a conclusion: i.e. it is generally a summary of the ideas developed in the body of the paragraph. Learn how to make transitions between paragraphs to signal relationships between ideas so as to create a fluent body of text. Do you want to know how to improve your English writing skills? Do you want to know how to write correct sentences without it being a painful task? Here are some tips to help you feel more confident with writing, and improve your English writing skills: 1. Read as much as you can.... An useful way to improve your English writing skills is to start your paragraphs with a topic sentence: i.e. a sentence that explains what you are going to write about. Continue with supporting sentences: i.e. sentences that provide more information about the topic. Finish with a conclusion: i.e. it is generally a summary of the ideas developed in the body of the paragraph. Learn how to make transitions between paragraphs to signal

relationships between ideas so as to create a fluent body of text.

We know that young children acquire vocabulary indirectly, first by listening when others speak or read to them, and then by using words to talk to others. As children begin to read and write, they acquire more words through understanding what they are reading and then incorporate those words into their speaking and writing. Vocabulary knowledge varies greatly among learners. The word knowledge gap between groups of children begins before they enter school. Why do some students have a richer, fuller vocabulary than some of their classmates?

- Language is rich with lots of verbal stimulation
- Wide background experiences
- Read to at home and at school
 - Read a lot independently
 - Early development of word consciousness
 - How Vocabulary Affects Reading Development

From the research, we know that vocabulary supports reading development and increases comprehension. Students with low vocabulary scores tend to have low comprehension and students with satisfactory or high vocabulary scores tend to have satisfactory or high comprehension scores.

The report of the National Reading Panel states that the complex process of comprehension is critical to the development of children's reading skills and cannot be understood without a clear understanding of the role that vocabulary development and instruction play in understanding what is read.

METHODOLOGY

1. Start with sentences to improve writing skills!

This tip is very obvious. As the building block of every text is the sentence. So, improving your sentences directly means improving your text.

But how can you improve your sentences? Here grammar and vocabulary play

key roles. In fact, looking at the IELTS band descriptor you can see that 50% of your writing skill mark is dedicated to English vocabulary and grammar or lexical resources.

When we talk about grammar we're talking about range and accuracy.

What is grammar range?

“It is the variety of grammatical structures you use. Like using different tenses or using complex sentences.”

What is accuracy?

“Accuracy means the correct use of grammar and avoiding mistakes.”

So clearly, the first step to improve writing skills is improving your grammar and vocabulary.

In fact, one of the biggest mistakes students who want to take part in the IELTS exam make is to start by learning the techniques of the IELTS exam however the first step should be improving your general English knowledge. 2. Improve writing skills by choosing the vocabulary and the style of writing vocabulary effect on improving writing skills

Look at these three sentences:

Shoes are designed to be destroyed one day. So you will need to buy another pair. The design philosophy of shoes includes their short life span, so as to create the urgency of replacement. It's part of the company's scheme of planned obsolescence to sell merchandise with a limited lifespan!

All three sentences have one meaning. So which one is better?

Well, you might say the third one or the second one is better than the first one. But it's not that way. All three can be good. It really depends on your audience. Choose your audience, choose your style to improve writing skills

Who are you writing for? Are you writing to a friend of yours? Maybe you're writing for a magazine or a newspaper or you want to post it on a website or maybe you are taking the IELTS or TOEFL exam or any other English exams.

Depending on your goal or your audience, you can use any of the three options. However, don't mix them up together!

If you are writing to a friend of yours, stick to a friendly tone. If you are writing for a magazine or a newspaper, stick to the formal tone. If you're taking part in the IELTS exam or TOEFL exam in the writing section, stick to your academic tone. So, tip number two is to keep the style and vocabulary coherent to improve writing skills.

Research shows that having a more active lifestyle will lead to better health. You can also use "research suggests that" or "there is evidence to suggest that". Now compare these three sentences:

Having a more active lifestyle leads to better health.

Research shows/research suggests that having a more active lifestyle leads to better health. There is evidence to suggest that having a more active lifestyle leads to better health.

As you can see, the second and the third ones sound very academic. By using these structures you will sound firm, strong, and evidence-based and it feels more academic.

Revise your text.

The final tip to improve writing skills is very simple but it is often ignored. Make sure you have enough time to go through your text again. By reading your text for a second time and if possible aloud, you will be able to recognize the little or big grammar mistakes that you have made. And you can correct some choices of vocabulary or the tone and style of your essay.

Sometimes, such a vocabulary is quite confusing. But it is very important to understand academic words and to be able to use them in your own writing. When you have a rich vocabulary, it will be easy to find right words that will perfectly suit your topic and the writing format. Moreover, it gives you more chances to write great papers and impress your teachers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The developing of the language skills has always been a very hard and an interesting task. The process of writing suggests that we can actually teach students how to write with coherence, an appropriate grammar structure and an acceptable spelling. One of the effective ways to do this is to motivate the students and make them aware of the steps involved in effective writing. Four reasons why students dislike writing are:

1. It leaves as more permanent record of proficiency than speaking; so it seems a threat for them.
2. Students feel that they lack sufficient knowledge of the language.
3. Students believe that writing must be grammatically correct.
4. They think that formal correctness must be achieved at their very first attempt.

The seven effective writing strategies are: 1) Pre-writing 2) early composing 3) planning and organizing 4) later composing 5) final composing 6) revising 7) editing (Writing: The creative process-116)

Development:

When we talk about writing is necessary to remember that there are three inseparable aspects when teaching it; Writing as a channel of a Foreign Language (FL) is the use of it alongside listening, speaking and reading in the process of learning important elements of the language; Writing as a goal of a FL learning , is the development of writing skills to fulfil such purposes as: note-taking, summarizing, narrating, reporting for various real-life situations and Writing with cohesion , is the employment of various linguistic means by which the parts of a written text are related to one another, with continuity and organization (The teaching of English as an International Language/Peter Wingard-143).

In our times, there is an increasing tendency of showing communication rather than the mere practice of linguistic forms. But we have to be careful because texts

are made of sentences putting together for communicative purposes. That is, you can not make bricks without straw and you can not build houses without bricks. So, to begin writing it is important to know the function of it, for instance, Advising, Reporting, etc.

But how can a teacher motivate the students for the writing activity?

The writing activities should be geared to their needs and interests. They should be linked to the real life whenever possible.

In our present work we pretend to give useful information about the developing of writing skills and give some practical teaching ideas for this purpose contributing to improve teacher's knowledge about this topic.

Then, we would like to state what the word PRACTICAL means. According to Webster's Dictionary it means 1) capable of being put to use, 2) useful thing, 3) disposed to action, 4) opposed to speculation or abstraction, 5) qualified by practice or practical training by experience and also concerned with ethical decisions. (Webster's Dictionary)

From our point of view, a practical teaching idea has something to do with a good idea, characterized by being attractive, exciting, applicable to real life and taking into account the environment, context and most of all, the learners 'needs and interests. Thus, teachers should know how to teach writing to be effective.

As it is known, writing is considered a very complex task for teachers and mainly for students. The heart of the language lessons is the communicative activity itself, so modern courses of English as a FL contain suggestions for many practical teaching ideas such as:

- Stimulations
- Language games
- Relevant writing activities like: short notes, commercials, stories, letters, postcards and others.

When trying to choose the right methodological approach for teaching

writing, questions like those below, always arise:

CONCLUSION

To recapitulate, developing writing skills to preparing IELTS and another exam is significant for learners who study foreign language. All of them should read a variety of articles, which related to international news and modern technologies to developing writing because they include that a lot of necessary to information in writing. For researches, for progressing writing students should read a variety of books, to try to write short story ,to watch different movies with subtitles which they can write with note. Teaching writing for teenagers is fundamental for their not only encouraging brain activity, but also psychological well being as well in advantageous ways. In this up-to-date globe, all of the individuals who have their own scientific skills are in high score stands. If human beings obey to following rules, they can open door for their prospect career opportunities over the cycle.

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